

Extended data: definitions of Narrative Policy Framework criteria

The below table defines the Narrative Policy Framework (NPF) criteria used in the methodology of the study "Capturing attention: media and institutional narratives on carbon capture, utilisation, and storage in three EU countries", which will be published on Open Research Europe. The components of the NPF are based on Brumbaugh and Rupp, 2020.

Component	Definition	Notes
Author position		
Pro-CCUS	Clear emotive appreciation and approval of CCUS technology/technologies	Can include or exclude scientific evidence
Anti-CCUS	Clear emotive opposition to CCUS technology/technologies	Can include or exclude scientific evidence
Matter-of-fact (pro)	Frames CCUS as positive using data/quotes but does not express pro-CCUS position	Necessarily includes scientific evidence
Matter-of-fact (anti)	Frames CCUS as negative using data/quotes but does not express anti-CCUS position	Necessarily includes scientific evidence
Hero	Those who take action with purpose to achieve the solution which the narrative is espousing or addressing the problem which concerns it.	E.g. sacrificing to solve a problem
Villain	Those who create a harm, or inflicts damage or pain upon a victim or, in other cases as one who opposes the aims of the hero.	E.g. being the cause of a problem
Victim	Those who are harmed by a particular action or inaction.	E.g. losing income because of a problem not caused by them
Plot: does it exist?		
Yes	There is a storyline in the narrative, rather than a collection of statements/facts	
No	There is no storyline in the narrative, it is rather a collection of statements/facts	
Plot (option 1)		
Stymied progress	The plot describes how things were terrible, got better due to a hero, but are getting worse because someone/thing is interfering with the hero's work.	
Story of decline	The plot describes how in the beginning things were good, but got worse, and are now so bad that something must be done.	
Change-is-only-an-illusion	The plot describes how everyone always thought things were getting worse(or better) but they were wrong the whole time, and how things are actually going in the opposite direction (decline or improvement was an illusion).	

Helplessness and control	The plot describes a situation as bad, and that it has always been believed the situation must be acceptable because it was unchangeable, but describes how can change can occur.	
Conspiracy	The plot describes a story moving from fate to control, but also having a twist ending that a certain small group knew how to control it all along and have been keeping control for their own benefit.	
Blame-the-victim	The plot describes a story moving from fate to control but locates the control in the hands of those suffering from the problem.	
Truth claim	The plot is centered around claiming a factual truth	
Victory	The plot describes how a battle between "good" and "bad" resulted in victory of "good"	
Other		
Plot (option 2)		
Climate/environmental effects narrative	The plot focuses on the climate/environmental effects of CCS	
Economic effects narrative	The plot focuses on the economic effects of CCS	
Employment narrative	The plot focuses on the employment effects of CCS	
Technology narrative	The plot focuses on the technological aspects of CCS	
Lock-in narrative	The plot focuses on CCS as a lock-in mechanism	E.g. legitimising fossil fuel usage, crowding out new clean energy technologies
Other		
Plot (option 3)		
CCUS is core in fossil world	The plot centres around the central importance of CCS in maintaining a fossil world	E.g. CCS as part of just transition to maintain fossil jobs
CCUS is nationally/regionally significant in mixed world	The plot centres around the national or regional significance of CCS in a partly fossil world	E.g. CCS as more than a niche application given continued partial reliance on fossil fuels
CCUS is niche in decarbonized world	The plot centres around CCS being applied to niche areas in a decarbonized world	E.g. CCS in specific industrial sectors
Other		
Causal mechanism: does it exist?		
Yes	Consequences and actions are discernible in the narrative	
No	Consequences and actions are not discernible in the narrative	
Causal mechanism: what type?		
Intentional	Does the excerpt associate intended consequences by purposeful actions with a policy problem/solution?	E.g. policymakers might be accused of favouring CCS to support business connections.

Mechanical	Does the excerpt associate intended consequences by unguided actions with a policy problem/solution?	E.g. a bad policy might be explained as resulting from an unthinking bureaucracy.
Inadvertent	Does the excerpt associate unintended consequences by purposeful action with a policy problem/solution?	E.g. the American Recovery and Reinvestment Act of 2009 might be explained as having raised inflation
Accidental	Does the excerpt associate unintended consequences by unguided actions with a policy problem/solution?	E.g. climate change might be explained as a natural occurrence having nothing to do with human action.
Other		
Policy stance adopted by the narrative		
Winning stance	Narrative adopts stance of "winning the war"	E.g. a CCS technology is solving climate change
Winning the battle, losing the war	Narrative adopts stance of winning a battle, but failing or needing to push more to win the war	E.g. a CCS technology could solve climate change, but is too expensive
Losing stance	Narrative adopts stance of "losing the war"	E.g. CCS can solve climate change, but it never will
Can't tell	Stance category cannot be determined	
No stance	No noticeable stance	
Projected to win	Narrative adopts stance that the supported policy is on a path to victory	E.g. CCS will emerge as the solution to climate change
Devil-shift	Narrative blames the opposition	E.g. an article placing disproportionate blame on opposition (even if causal mechanisms are not clear, or are accidental)
Angel-shift	Narrative glorifies the coalition's actions as heroic	E.g. an article speaking reverentially of technology developers (usually associated with ignoring risks)
Extreme stance	Narrative adopts a black-and-white view of CCUS	E.g., "CCUS is inevitable" or conversely "CCUS is nothing more than fossil lock-in"

References

Brumbaugh, Amelia, and John A. Rupp. 2020. "Wabash CarbonSAFE Subtask 4.1 - Application of Policy Frameworks for Improved Carbon Capture and Storage Social Site Characterization & Stakeholder Engagement." DOE-FE0031626-2. Univ. of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, IL (United States). <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/1664756>.